

NOTES

4. L. JOEL KIRKPATRICH (Gulf oil Corp.) U. S. 4,097,263; *Chem. Abs.*, 1979, **90**, 38928e.
5. K. AVASTHI, Ph.D. Thesis, "Search for New Pesticides", Lucknow University, Lucknow (1975).
6. R. P. RAO and J. N. SINGH, *Vigyan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1973, **16**, 73.
7. R. M. DODSON and C. L. KING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 871; 1950, **72**, 3722.
8. S. P. COLOWICK and N. O. KAPLAN, "Methods in enzymology, Academic Press", New York.
9. S. HESTRIN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1949, **180**, 249.
3. G. V. SATYAVATHI, D. N. PRASAD, S. P. SEN and P. K. DAS, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1969, **57**, 437; 1970 **58**, 660; 1970, **58**, 947.
4. S. MUKERJI, A. K. BANERJEE and B. N. MITRA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1970, **32**, 48.
5. SUDHIR AGRAWAL and K. MISRA, *Chemica Scripta*, 1977, **12**, 37.
6. SUDHIR AGRAWAL and K. MISRA, *Planta Medica*, 1980, **38**, 277.
7. SUDHIR AGRAWAL and K. MISRA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, **48**, 141.

**Leucoanthocyanidins from *Saraca asoca*
Stem Bark**

J. KAUR DUGGAL and K. MISRA

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

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S. asoca (Ashoka : N. O. Leguminosae) is well known for its medicinal properties. Its highly astringent stem bark is used in uterine affections in menorrhagia and scorpion sting¹. In the past, some chemical constituents have been reported to be present in this bark^{2,3,4}. The bark was extracted with acetone at room temperature and the concentrated viscous mass was subsequently macerated with petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol respectively.

The light petroleum extracted some waxy matter along with β -sitosterol. The ethylacetate extract on fractional precipitation with light petrol yielded a homogeneous compound (A). The acetone fraction on column chromatography on silica gel afforded compound (B), methanol fraction on repeated crystallisation with methanol-ethyl acetate yielded a homogeneous entity (C).

From a study of colour reactions, UV spectral data, acid hydrolysis, degradation, co-chromatography, mp, mmp compound (A) $C_{21}H_{24}O_{11}$ was identified as leucopelargonidin 3-O- β -D-glucoside by the well known procedure^{5,6}. Compound (B) $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ was found to be identical with leucopelargonidin⁷ and compound (C) $C_{15}H_{14}O_7$ with leucocyanidin⁷.

The high astringency of the bark can be ascribed to the presence of these flavan-diols, and to the highly water soluble glycoside.

References

1. I. MUKERJI, S. BANERJI and A. K. MITRA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1970, **32**, 48.
2. S. P. SEN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, **32**, 502.

**Studies on Heterocyclic Primary Amines. III :
Synthesis of N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)
Triphenyl Imidophosphoranes**

M. EL-DEEK, E. EL-SAWI and K. EL-BADRY

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and University
College for Women, Ain-Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

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IMIDOPHOSPHORANES in which the nitrogen atom is attached to heterocyclic ring are rare. Because of the increasing biological¹⁻⁶ and industrial⁷ uses of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives, we became interested in the preparation of new types of 1,3,4-oxadiazolylimidophosphoranes(I).

(I)

Ar

a = C_6H_5 , b = *m*- ClC_6H_4 , c = *p*- ClC_6H_4 ,
d = *p*- $CH_3C_6H_4$, e = *p*- $CH_3OC_6H_4$

The synthetic route which was found to be most convenient for the desired heterocyclic imidophosphoranes(I) employed the method of Horner and Oediger⁸. Thus, on subjecting 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole to dibromotriphenylphosphorane in dry benzene in the presence of triethylamine, at room temperature followed by four hours' reflux under nitrogen, the desired imidophosphoranes(I) were obtained in 70-80% yield.

The i.r. spectra of all the compounds(I) showed a band at about 1300 cm^{-1} due to the N=P stretching vibration^{9a} with the concomitant disappearance of the NH stretching vibration at 3140 cm^{-1} present in the starting aminooxadiazoles. The P-C (aromatic) stretching absorption was observed for all the compounds at 1440 cm^{-1} ^{9b}. The i.r. spectra of all the compounds(I) also showed the cyclic C=N stretching bands at $1640\text{-}1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$.